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Formulation and Stability Analysis of a Multi-Scale Modeling Approach for Simulation of Elastic Wave Propagation*

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In this work, we report on the formulation and detailed stability analysis of a dynamic multi-scale scheme involving two different local computational strategies for modeling of elastic wave propagation. The coupled model involves the Local Interaction Simulation Approach and Cellular Automata for Elastodynamics, however the presented analysis approach is general and applies to other numerical techniques. This scheme is capable of coupling two numerical models with possibly dissimilar spatial discretization lengths and material properties, hence it is appealing for a multi-scale and/or multi-resolution analysis. The method developed in this paper employs an interface force–displacement coupling to yield the multi-scale model equations. It is shown that the governing equations contain a self-coupling term that affects the stability of the system, as it contributes to additional stiffness at the interface. Stability analysis is presented in terms of rotations of two vectors in β space, where each vector represents individual model's stability. Three model configurations of practical interest were investigated, analytical formulae derived and used to analyze stability. These analytical formulae were compared against results from numerical simulations and perfect agreement was observed.

Keywords: Dynamic coupling; stability analysis; elastic wave propagation; finite differences; cellular automata.

*This work is further developed based on the original work presented at ICCM2020.

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1. Introduction

Elastic waves are widely employed in various disciplines of science and industry [Cheeke (2017)] owing to their unique response after interacting with structural features. Example applications may include material characterization [Chimenti (2014)], sensing and imaging [Fenster and Downey (1996)], evaluation of structural state [Raghavan and Cesnik (2007)], manipulation [Qiu *et al.* (2014)], cutting [Thoe *et al.* (1998)], welding [Kumar *et al.* (2017)] and much more [Vilkhu *et al.* (2008); Muthukumar *et al.* (2006); Plotino *et al.* (2007)]. Development of the techniques listed above requires design, prototyping and testing — typically an iterative and costly processes. In such cases, numerical modeling is frequently employed as a supporting tool, allowing for predicting complex wavefields and limiting the need for expensive and time-consuming physical experiments.

Various applications of elastic waves require detailed analysis at different scales of time and space. For example, in damage detection applications, time and space scales of crack propagation are typically much smaller than those of wave propagation through the structure. Accurate treatment of both — small and large — scales calls for a multi-scale modeling approach that involves decomposition of the domain of interest into subdomains of different scales between which information is exchanged. The treatment of the interface between the subdomains — i.e., the information transfer process — distinguishes one coupling method from another. Two categories of coupling methods in the concurrent multi-scale models can be found, namely, overlapping and nonoverlapping (interface) subdomains coupling. The former generates a single global energy functional that approximates the total energy of the system, while the latter involves developing boundary conditions and local solution of each of the subdomains until convergence is reached [Parks *et al.* (2008)]. The analysis can either consider static or dynamic effects, consequently relating to spatial and spatio-temporal coupling, respectively.

Static coupling requires finding force–displacement equilibrium of the system. Iterative techniques are typically employed to correct positions and forces. Tadmor *et al.* [1996] proposed the quasicontinuum (QC) method to achieve static atomistic–continuum coupling for analyzing defects in solids. In Shilkrot *et al.* [2002] static coupling of the QC method with continuum defect models was introduced. Recently, a new method to couple different length scales of finite element method (FEM) meshes with Peridynamic (PD) grids was proposed in Zaccariotto *et al.* [2017]. The method was an extension of a previous work, that required FEM meshes and PD grids to have the same spacing, and introduced fictitious FEM and PD nodes to achieve the static coupling. As local and nonlocal methods were coupled, special treatment of the interface was required.

Although iterative static coupling techniques can be employed to determine equilibrium in each time step of dynamic analysis, such application can be ineffective due to a number of operations per time step required for convergence. Therefore, substantially different methods are needed for coupling of dynamic fields that maintain high efficiency of numerical models for wave propagation. Extension of

static coupling to dynamic transient coupling is a major challenge as physical fields need to be dynamically exchanged between the subdomains as the simulation progresses. Various techniques have been proposed to achieve dynamic coupling for discrete–continuum and continuum–continuum systems that address the respective scale-specific problems. For example, in an atomistic–continuum dynamic coupling, as phonons cannot be represented in the continuum model, they reflect at the interface causing local heating of the atomistic domain and destroying the simulation [Weinan and Huang (2002)]. In Weinan and Huang [2002], a dynamic atomistic–continuum coupling method for molecular dynamics and conventional finite difference method (FDM) was presented and used for modeling defects in crystalline materials. This method used a class of matching conditions between the atomistic and continuum regions that ensured minimum reflection of phonons at the interface and accurate passage of large-scale information between the atomistic and continuum regions. A bridging scale approach — based on projection of the molecular dynamics solution onto the coarse scale shape functions — for dynamic coupling of continuum mechanics with molecular dynamics was proposed in Wagner and Liu [2003].

Dynamic transient coupling has been also used to couple two continuum models, and its application to simulation of elastic waves started by coupling analytical and FEMs. Koshiha *et al.* [1984] used a method based on coupling of analytical and FEMs to analyze the scattering of the fundamental symmetric Lamb wave in an elastic plate. Moulin *et al.* [2000] proposed a method for coupling FEM and normal mode expansion method. More recently, Gao and Keyes [2019] presented a coupling of FEM with FDM for isotropic elastic wave simulations in an energy-conserving manner. In that work, the coupling was achieved via weakly imposed interface conditions and modification of the FEM and FDM equations.

In its first part, this paper reports on the formulation of a dynamic hybrid coupling scheme with a potential use in multi-scale analysis. A minimal-overlapping domain coupling approach is followed that can be used to couple any continuum models for elastic wave propagation with possibly dissimilar spatial discretization lengths and material properties. Here, we employ the proposed coupling scheme for two local methods for modeling elastic wave propagation, i.e., the Local Interaction Simulation Approach (LISA) — a very efficient technique based on finite differences and implemented with graphical processing units [Delsanto *et al.* (1994); Leamy *et al.* (2014); Packo *et al.* (2015)] — with Cellular Automata for Elastodynamics (CAFE) — a bottom-up modeling strategy capable of employing both rectangular and triangular meshes [Leamy (2008); Hopman and Leamy (2011); Leamy *et al.* (2014)]. This particular selection aims at making use of CAFE’s capability to allow nonuniform mesh in regions requiring fine resolution — e.g., crack vicinity — and LISA’s efficiency in the remaining portion of the domain. A detailed analysis of numerical dispersion and performance of the methods can be found in Leamy [2008] and Packo *et al.* [2015, 2020].

The coupling scheme proposed here is noninvasive and does not impact the structure of individual models, hence does not modify their respective equations. The model couples the (initially) stress-free boundaries of the models via force and displacement continuity. Technically, the coupling is realized through Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions. This is in contrast to other existing continuum coupling schemes (e.g. Gao and Keyes [2019] or Zaccariotto *et al.* [2017]), where the equations of the coupled models are modified. Using the proposed coupling scheme, existing numerical solvers can be used without the need for changing their codes.

It is known that for convergence of a numerical (FD) scheme, the Lax equivalence theorem [Lax and Richtmyer (1956)] requires stability and consistency. The former relates to quantitative measure of the well-posedness of the discrete problem, while the latter — to a quantitative measure of the extent to which the exact solution satisfies the discrete problem Arnold (2015). In particular, consistency issues may include model accuracy in predicting wavefields, e.g., artificial reflections from domains' boundaries. In this paper, we focus on the stability, leaving the analysis of consistency — and therefore error quantification — for follow-up work.

As coupling methods in dynamics involve time integration schemes, they are prone to stability issues. Implicit time integration schemes, some of which are unconditionally stable, permit large time steps, but the cost per step is high and storage requirements tend to increase dramatically with the size of the mesh. Explicit time integration schemes, on the other hand, are conditionally stable, but inexpensive per time step and require less storage than implicit schemes [Liu *et al.* (1991)]. In elastic wave propagation simulations, usually explicit time integration schemes are favorable because the requirement of small time step — needed for stability — is a natural choice due to the inherent high temporal resolution of a simulation. Stability analysis has been reported for both single-scale and coupled dynamic simulations. A theoretical approach to analyze the stability of the finite difference–time domain (FDTD) method applied to electromagnetic problems was proposed in Min *et al.* [1990]. This approach was based on the Fourier (von Neumann) method. Remis [2000] presented a necessary and sufficient condition for stability of the FDTD method. Elastic wave propagation modeling in 3D velocity–stress FD formulation was investigated for stability in Hestholm [2003]. Heselhaus [1998] presented a hybrid coupling scheme and stability analysis for coupled solid/fluid turbine blade temperature calculations. That work involved coupling of finite elements with a finite volume Navier–Stokes time marching flow solver, and the stability analysis of the coupling scheme was carried out analytically and numerically. Rao and Wang [2019] derived explicitly the numerical dispersion relation and the stability condition for the computation of a 2D pseudo-acoustic wave equation. Qi-Zhen *et al.* [2015] adopted a hybrid pseudospectral–finite difference scheme to solve the pure P-wave equation and investigated its stability by the von Neumann's method.

Following the coupling method formulation, the second part of this paper is devoted to detailed stability analysis of the proposed multi-scale coupling scheme. The analysis is based on the von Neumann approach, similar to Min *et al.* [1990]

and Qi-Zhen *et al.* [2015], however, it is developed for a coupled model and, hence, includes discretization and material parameters of two, rather than one, models. As a consequence, the stability is analyzed using two vectors — each representing an individual model’s stability — that rotate in the stability space in opposite directions, and their critical combinations drive the stability of the coupled model. This contrasts with the case of an explicit time integration scheme, where the stability is given by a single vector in the stability space. Examples presented in this work consider different model configurations of practical importance. An analytical study of stability of a multi-scale scheme, i.e. including more than one numerical model at a time — to the best of the authors’ knowledge — has not been reported in literature.

This paper is organized as follows. First, LISA and CAFE are introduced briefly, followed by the formulation of a dynamic hybrid multi-scale coupling scheme. Next, equations at the interface, where CAFE and LISA domains meet, are derived and used to analyze the stability of the coupling scheme. This paper reports a complete stability analysis of the scheme and extreme conditions (stability limits) are presented in terms of two vectors in the β (stability parameter) space. Next, the stability of the multi-scale scheme is analyzed for three configurations, namely, no restrictions on coupled models’ parameters, equal stiffnesses, and equal stiffnesses and densities in the models. For each of these configurations, analytical formulae are derived allowing for determining the critical time step value for a given set of model parameters. Next, these analytical formulae are validated against numerical simulations. In the last section, conclusions from the analyzes are drawn.

2. Problem Formulation

The multi-scale dynamic coupling strategy developed and analyzed in this paper can be applied in any dimension. Practical applications require at least 2D setups, however the governing equations for that cases are rather lengthy and more difficult to interpret. Therefore, we start by introducing the fundamental concepts in 1D, followed by a brief outline of 2D systems. Next, dynamic properties of 1D and 2D problems formulated via continuum mechanics and local computational modeling frameworks, namely the LISA and CAFE, will be studied. Finally, a multi-scale coupling procedure for analysis will be developed and applied in terms of stability.

Throughout this paper, capitalized letters A , B , U , ΔX and ΔY will refer to the LISA domain, and lower-case letters, a , b , c , u , Δx and Δy — to the CAFE domain.

2.1. Wave propagation in 1D space

We consider a 1D medium with the only displacement degrees of freedom (DOF) being U . The wave equation for a 1D elastic continuous medium can be written as

$$\sigma_{,x} = \rho U_{,tt}, \tag{1}$$

where ρ is the density, σ denotes the stress tensor and indexes after comma denote differentiation with respect to that quantity. For a 1D linear elastic medium, the stress relates to the strain via Hooke's law, $\sigma = E\varepsilon = Eu_{,x}$, where E is the Young's modulus. Equation (1) holds for a point in an infinite medium.

2.1.1. *LISA model in 1D*

The elastic medium is discretized into a grid of points labeled by integer numbers n . The space between points is occupied by an elastic material, possibly different between each two adjacent points. For discretization of Eq. (1), we consider a grid point n and its closest neighbors $n - 1$ (to the left of n) and $n + 1$ (to the right of n). The space between grid points $n - 1$ and n is occupied by material A , while the space between n and $n + 1$ — by material B . A schematic of the grid is shown in Fig. 1(a). Discretizing Eq. (1) at n would require evaluation of $\sigma_{,x}$ at the discontinuity of two adjacent materials. As Eq. (1) holds individually in each cell, we consider two points near n but spaced δ from it at both sides of the interface. Thus, we have

$$\rho^A U_{n-\delta,tt} = \sigma_{n-\delta,x} \quad \text{and} \quad \rho^B U_{n+\delta,tt} = \sigma_{n+\delta,x}. \tag{2}$$

Since there is no discontinuity inside each cell, Hooke's law is applied along with the first-order Euler finite difference formulas to evaluate the stresses in Eq. (2) as

$$\sigma_{n-\delta,x} = \frac{2E^A}{\Delta X} (U_{n-\delta,x} - U_{n-\frac{1}{2},x}), \quad \sigma_{n+\delta,x} = \frac{2E^B}{\Delta X} (U_{n-\frac{1}{2},x} - U_{n+\delta,x}), \tag{3}$$

where ΔX is the distance between two adjacent nodes. Owing to the discontinuity of material properties at n , the first-order derivatives $U_{n\mp\delta,x}$ cannot be evaluated. However, stress continuity conditions at n can be used to remove them

$$\sigma_{n-\delta} = \sigma_{n+\delta} \Leftrightarrow E^A U_{n-\delta,x} = E^B U_{n+\delta,x}. \tag{4}$$

Assuming that there is no discontinuity in the initial displacement field and $\delta \ll \Delta X$, displacements at $n \mp \delta$ converge toward common value,

Fig. 1. LISA grids for 1D (a) and 2D (b) setups.

$U_{n-\delta,tt} = U_{n+\delta,tt} = U_{n,tt}$. Next, adding Eqs. (2) and using (3) and (4) yields

$$\frac{E^B}{\Delta X^2}(U_{n+1} - U_{n-1}) - \frac{E^A}{\Delta X^2}(U_n - U_{n-1}) = \frac{\rho^A + \rho^B}{2}U_{n,tt}. \quad (5)$$

The right-hand side of Eq. (5) requires evaluation of $U_{,tt}$ which depends on the time integration scheme adopted and — for the explicit approach typically employed for wave propagation — yields $U_{,tt} \approx (U_n^{t+1} - 2U_n^t + U_n^{t-1})/\Delta t^2$. The equivalent density (corresponding to a mass-lumping procedure) can be taken as an average of the two, i.e., $\rho = (\rho^A + \rho^B)/2$.

The final iteration equation of LISA in 1D can be written as

$$U_n^{t+1} = 2U_n^t - U_n^{t-1} + \frac{\Delta t^2}{\rho \Delta X^2}[E^B U_{n+1} - (E^A + E^B)U_n + E^A U_{n-1}]. \quad (6)$$

2.1.2. CAFE model in 1D

We consider a 1D medium with the only displacement DOF being u . The elastic medium is discretized into a grid of points labeled by integer numbers n , as shown in Fig. 2(a). In contrast to LISA, here each point lies at the center of a cell, which is occupied by an elastic material. The balance of momentum for the cell can be written as

$$mu_{n,tt} = \sum F = F_R - F_L, \quad (7)$$

where m is the mass of cell b , $u_{n,tt}$ is the second time derivative of displacement, and $\sum F$ denotes the summation of forces acting on the cell, i.e., forces from the right, F_R , and from the left, F_L , cells.

The forces from Eq. (7) can be subsequently written in terms of relative displacements of neighboring cells, $n - 1$ (to the left of n) and $n + 1$ (to the right of n). For possibly different materials associated with the three cells, the grid point $n - 1$ is surrounded by material a , n — by material b , and $n + 1$ — by material c .

Fig. 2. CAFE grids for 1D (a) and 2D (b) setups.

Then, the forces F_R and F_L are evaluated as

$$F_R = \sigma_R(\Delta y w) \quad \text{and} \quad F_L = \sigma_L(\Delta y w), \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta y w$ is the cross-section area of the cell. As Hooke's law holds individually in each cell, the stresses σ_R and σ_L are given by

$$\sigma_R = \left(\frac{E^b + E^c}{2} \right) \left(\frac{u_{n+1} - u_n}{\Delta x} \right), \quad \sigma_L = \left(\frac{E^a + E^b}{2} \right) \left(\frac{u_n - u_{n-1}}{\Delta x} \right), \quad (9)$$

where Δx is the distance between two adjacent grid points.

Using Eqs. (8) and (9) in Eq. (7), we get

$$u_{n,tt} = \frac{\sum F}{m} = \frac{1}{2\Delta x^2 \rho^b} [(E^b + E^c)u_{n+1} - (E^a + 2E^b + E^c)u_n + (E^a + E^b)u_{n-1}]. \quad (10)$$

The left-hand side of Eq. (10) requires evaluation of m at cell b , where $m = \Delta x(\Delta y w)\rho^b$, and $u_{n,tt}$. The latter depends on the time integration scheme adopted and — for the explicit approach — yields $u_{n,tt} \approx (u_n^{t+1} - 2u_n^t + u_n^{t-1})/\Delta t^2$. The final iteration equation for CAFE is then written as

$$u_n^{t+1} = 2u_n^t - u_n^{t-1} + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2\Delta x^2 \rho^b} [(E^b + E^c)u_{n+1} - (E^a + 2E^b + E^c)u_n + (E^a + E^b)u_{n-1}]. \quad (11)$$

2.2. Wave propagation in 2D space

We consider a 2D medium with displacement DOFs collected in vector $\mathbf{Q} = [U \ V]^T$. The wave equation for a 2D linear elastic continuous medium can be written as

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \rho \mathbf{Q}_{,tt}, \quad (12)$$

where ρ is the mass density, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor. For a linear elastic isotropic medium the stress-strain relation is given as $\sigma_{11} = (\lambda + 2\mu)\epsilon_{11} + \lambda\epsilon_{22}$, $\sigma_{22} = (\lambda + 2\mu)\epsilon_{22} + \lambda\epsilon_{11}$ and $\sigma_{12} = 2\mu\epsilon_{1,2}$, where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \{\epsilon_{i,j}\} = 1/2(\mathbf{Q}_{i,j} + \mathbf{Q}_{j,i})$ is the strain tensor, and λ and μ are the Lamé constants. In the 2D analysis, invariance of material properties distribution along the vertical direction is assumed.

2.2.1. LISA model in 2D

For the 2D case, Eq. (12) is discretized using a uniform grid of rectangles with the material properties and displacements assigned to cells and nodes, respectively, as shown in Fig. 1(b). Owing to the assumption of invariance of material distribution along the vertical direction, cells 2 and 3 are occupied by material A , and cells 1 and 4 are occupied by material B . Following a procedure analogous to that of Sec. 2.1.1 — and using the vertical translational symmetry with the phase relation

$Q_{n,m\pm 1} = Q_n e^{\pm i(K_Y \Delta Y)}$ — the final 2D LISA iteration equation for a grid point located at the intersection of four adjacent material cells is written as

$$Q_n^{t+1} = 2Q_n^t - Q_n^{t-1} + \frac{\Delta t^2}{\rho} [\kappa_R Q_{n+1} - \kappa_M Q_n + \kappa_L Q_{n-1}], \quad (13)$$

where $\rho = \frac{\rho^{(1)} + \rho^{(2)} + \rho^{(3)} + \rho^{(4)}}{4}$ represents the density at the intersection of four adjacent material cells, $Q_{n+c_n}^{t+c_t} = [U_{n+c_n,m}^{t+c_t}, V_{n+c_n,m}^{t+c_t}]^T$, $c_t, c_n \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$. Note that due to the phase relation, all the vectors in Eq. (13) refer to the m th vertical node (subscript dropped for clarity). κ_L , κ_M and κ_R are populated with stiffness coefficients related to displacements of left (Q_{n-1}), middle (Q_n) and right (Q_{n+1}) vertical group of cells. Detailed information on the LISA derivation in 2D can be found in Appendix A and Delsanto *et al.* [1994], Paćko *et al.*, Leamy *et al.* [2014] and Packo *et al.* [2020].

2.2.2. CAFE model in 2D

For the CAFE 2D case, the grid is composed of nine neighboring cells as shown in Fig. 2(b). Like in the case of LISA 2D, the assumption of invariance of material distribution along the vertical direction causes cells 2, 7 and 3 to be occupied by material a , cells 6, 0 and 8 to be occupied by material b , and cells 1, 5 and 4 to be occupied by material c . The balance of momentum for the central cell is written as

$$m\mathbf{q}_{,tt} = \sum \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{F}^S, \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{F}^T and \mathbf{F}^S represent tensile and shear force vectors, respectively.

$$\mathbf{F}^T = \begin{bmatrix} F_R^{xx} - F_L^{xx} \\ F_T^{yy} - F_B^{yy} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F}^S = \begin{bmatrix} F_T^{xy} - F_B^{xy} \\ F_R^{xy} - F_L^{xy} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Following the procedure analogous to that of Sec. 2.1.2 — and using the vertical translational symmetry with the phase relation $q_{n,m\pm 1} = q_n e^{\pm i(k_y \Delta y)}$ as in Sec. 2.2.1 — the final 2D CAFE iteration equation for the central cell is written as

$$q_n^{t+1} = 2q_n^t - q_n^{t-1} + \frac{\Delta t^2}{\Delta x \Delta y \rho^b} [\kappa_r q_{n+1} - \kappa_m q_n + \kappa_l q_{n-1}], \quad (15)$$

where $q_{n+c_n}^{t+c_t} = [u_{n+c_n,m}^{t+c_t}, v_{n+c_n,m}^{t+c_t}]^T$, $c_t, c_n \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$. κ_l , κ_m and κ_r are populated with stiffness coefficients related to displacements of left (q_{n-1}), middle (q_n) and right (q_{n+1}) vertical group of cells. Like in Eq. (13), all the vectors in Eq. (15) belong to the m th vertical node. Detailed information on CAFE model in 2D along with κ_l , κ_m and κ_r can be found in Appendix B.

3. Multi-Scale Coupling Strategy

The proposed multi-scale scheme will couple two different numerical models. In this work, LISA and CAFE methods are employed in the model. The analysis domain is

subdivided into two parts, the left part modeled by LISA and the right — by CAFE. The interface — a node in 1D and a (vertical) line of nodes in 2D — is located at the center of the analysis domain. At the interface, LISA and CAFE have initially stress-free boundaries. The multi-scale coupling strategy assumes exchange of information (data) between the models only at the interface by prescribing Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions to each of the models. The boundary conditions are mutually coupled, i.e., the LISA domain is loaded by a boundary condition that depends on the results from the CAFE domain and vice versa. Specifically, displacements from CAFE are coupled to LISA via the Dirichlet boundary condition, and forces computed in the LISA domain are passed to the CAFE domain through the Neumann boundary condition. Consequently, the computation of displacements in CAFE is dependent on LISA’s forces, and the force computation in LISA depends on CAFE’s displacements. This leads to a self-coupled scheme wherein elastic and inertial forces are coupled dynamically. Note that although the proposed approach couples two specific numerical schemes, the general idea of coupling displacements and stresses would work for any two methods that allow for computation of those quantities and imposing displacement and force boundary conditions.

3.1. The interface equation in 1D

The model setup for the 1D case is presented in Fig. 3(a). The displacement boundary condition on the LISA node, U_n , is directly transferred from the CAFE boundary u_n , i.e., $U_n = u_n$. Based on the reaction force from the LISA domain, $F_{1/2}^B = \sigma_{1/2}^B(\Delta y w)$, the force boundary condition is applied to the left side of the CAFE cell, i.e., $F_L = F_{1/2}^B$. This latter condition, along with the assumption of constant cross-sectional area of the 1D medium, implies stress continuity condition.

Fig. 3. Grid arrangements for 1D (a) and 2D (b) setups of the multi-scale coupled models. The coupling zone, with its left, L , and right, R , boundaries is marked by dashed lines. Note the models overlap in the coupling zone.

Fig. 3. (Continued)

The interface boundary conditions can be written as

$$U_n = u_n \quad \text{and} \quad F_L = F_{1/2}^B = \frac{E^B(U_n - U_{n-1})}{\Delta X} (\Delta y w). \quad (16)$$

According to the outlined above data exchange between the models, the interface node equation can be formulated. The dynamics of the interface node, n , is governed by a CAFE iteration equation with appropriate left-hand side force boundary condition. Using Eq. (16) and the iteration equations, Eqs. (6) and (11), after some manipulations yields the coupled node equation

$$u_n^{t+1} - 2u_n - \alpha \left[\frac{\bar{E}}{\Delta x} u_{n+1} - \left(\frac{\bar{E}}{\Delta x} + \frac{E^B}{\Delta X} \right) u_n + \frac{E^B}{\Delta X} U_{n-1} \right] + u_n^{t-1} = 0, \quad (17)$$

where $2\bar{E} = E^b + E^c$ and $\alpha = \Delta t^2 / (\rho^b \Delta x)$.

The coupling formula, (17), is a CAFE equation that involves the LISA solution, U_{n-1} , computed by using Eq. (6). Equation (6), on the other hand, requires U_n which — via Eq. (16) — is given by (17). Clearly, the coupling equation contains a CAFE–CAFE self-coupling term, which is critical for stability of the multi-scale model.

For subsequent stability analysis, it is convenient to rewrite Eq. (17) as

$$u_n^{t+1} - \alpha \hat{\kappa} u_{n+1} + 2(\alpha \bar{\kappa} - 1)u_n - \alpha \kappa U_{n-1} + u_n^{t-1} = 0, \tag{18}$$

with $\kappa = \frac{E^B}{\Delta X}$, $\hat{\kappa} = \frac{\bar{E}}{\Delta x}$ and $\bar{\kappa} = (\kappa + \hat{\kappa})/2$.

3.2. The interface equation in 2D

In the 2D case, the cell discretization lengths in the vertical direction were assumed to be equal, i.e. $\Delta y = \Delta Y$. The coupling setup for the 2D case is presented in Fig. 3(b). At the interface, all the LISA nodes at the vertical line were coupled to CAFE nodes. Then, similar to the 1D case, for each interface node, the displacement boundary condition on the LISA node, \mathbf{Q}_n , is directly transferred from the CAFE boundary \mathbf{q}_n , i.e., $\mathbf{Q}_n = \mathbf{q}_n$. Based on the reaction forces — tensile (F_m^{xx}) and shear (F_m^{xy}) forces — from the LISA domain, the force boundary condition is applied to the left side of the m th coupled CAFE cell (F_L^{xx} and F_L^{xy}). The interface boundary conditions for the m th cell at the vertical line can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q}_n &= \mathbf{q}_n, \\ F_L^{xx} &= F_m^{xx} = \left[\frac{\lambda_L + 2\mu_L}{\Delta X} \text{i}2 \frac{\lambda_L}{4\Delta Y} \sin(K_Y \Delta Y) \right] \begin{bmatrix} (U_{n+1,m} - U_{n,m}) \\ V_{n,m} \end{bmatrix} (\Delta Y w), \\ F_L^{xy} &= F_m^{xy} = \left[\frac{\mu_L}{\Delta X} \text{i}2 \frac{\mu_L}{4\Delta Y} \sin(K_Y \Delta Y) \right] \begin{bmatrix} (V_{n+1,m} - V_{n,m}) \\ U_{n,m} \end{bmatrix} (\Delta Y w), \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

where λ_L and μ_L are Lamé constants of the LISA domain (λ_C and μ_C will refer to the CAFE domain). The interface equation can be formulated — for the m th vertical node — as

$$\mathbf{q}_n^{t+1} - \alpha \hat{\kappa} \mathbf{q}_{n+1} + 2(\alpha \bar{\kappa} - \mathbf{I})\mathbf{q}_n - \alpha \kappa \mathbf{Q}_{n-1} + \mathbf{q}_n^{t-1} = 0, \tag{20}$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, $\hat{\kappa}$ and κ are related to LISA and CAFE stiffness, respectively, while $\bar{\kappa}$ relates to stiffness contributions from both LISA and CAFE, and are given as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\kappa} &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(\lambda_C + 2\mu_C)}{\Delta x} \Delta y & \text{i} \frac{\lambda_C}{2} \sin(k_y \Delta y) + \text{i} \frac{\mu_C}{4} \sin(k_y \Delta y) \\ \text{i} \frac{\mu_C}{2} \sin(k_y \Delta y) + \text{i} \frac{\lambda_C}{4} \sin(k_y \Delta y) & \frac{\mu_C}{\Delta x} \Delta y \end{bmatrix}, \\ \bar{\kappa} &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\mu_C}{\Delta y} \Delta x (1 - \cos(k_y \Delta y)) & \\ + \frac{\lambda_C + 2\mu_C}{2\Delta x} \Delta y + \frac{\lambda_L + 2\mu_L}{2\Delta X} \Delta Y & -\text{i} \frac{\lambda_C}{4} \sin(k_y \Delta y) \\ -\text{i} \frac{\mu_C}{4} \sin(k_y \Delta y) & \frac{\lambda_C + 2\mu_C}{\Delta y} \Delta x (1 - \cos(k_y \Delta y)) \\ & + \frac{\mu_C}{2\Delta x} \Delta y + \frac{\mu_L}{2\Delta X} \Delta Y \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\kappa = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\lambda_L + 2\mu_L}{\Delta X} \Delta Y & -i2\lambda_L \sin(K_Y \Delta Y) \\ -i2\mu_L \sin(K_Y \Delta Y) & \frac{\mu_L}{\Delta X} \Delta Y \end{bmatrix}.$$

3.3. Energy conservation at the interface

Numerical schemes, in particular FD methods, often experience energy conservation issues, some of them resolving the problem better than the other. In case of dynamic transient schemes, the energy conservation is influenced by two factors — temporal (time discretization methods) as well as spatial (space discretization techniques). Both LISA and CAFE, as successors of finite difference techniques, suffer from energy conservation issues, however, they are proven to be efficient and accurate for elastic wave propagation simulations Paćko *et al.* (2012); Hopman and Leamy (2011), provided that proper discretization parameters are selected Paćko *et al.* (2020). The coupling scheme proposed here does not add any stabilization or dissipative terms — hence no energy is lost or added (up to the numerical dissipation). This is confirmed by the validations of stability conditions reported in Sec. 6, where the incident wave energy is distributed between reflected and transmitted waves, with no observable absorption. The amount of reflection depends on the mismatch of numerical dispersion across the interface, and will occur even for nominally the same material properties of the domains, as observed in Figs. 10(a), 10(c) and 10(e). Detailed studies of these artificial reflections are beyond the scope of this paper and will be a topic of a follow-up work.

4. Stability Analysis of the Coupled Scheme in 1D

The self-coupling property of the multi-scale scheme, as can be seen from Eqs. (17) and (20), results in a nonobvious stability for the explicit time integration scheme used for wave propagation. Hence, a stability analysis is required to find the critical time step $\hat{\Delta}t$ of the coupled model and its dependence on parameters of the models.

Assuming the propagating wave of frequency ω and wavenumbers K and k in LISA and CAFE domains, respectively, and introducing phase factors $u_{n+1} = e^{ik\Delta x} u_n$ and $U_{n-1} = e^{-iK\Delta X} U_n = e^{-iK\Delta X} u_n$, and $u_n^{t+1} = g^2$, $u_n^t = g$ and $u_n^{t-1} = 1$ into (17) gives the amplification polynomial

$$g^2 - [\alpha\hat{\kappa}e^{ik\Delta x} + \alpha\kappa e^{-iK\Delta X} - 2(\alpha\bar{\kappa} - 1)]g + 1 = 0. \quad (21)$$

It is required for stability that the roots of Eq. (21), $g_{1,2}$, satisfy $|g_{1,2}| \leq 1$ or — equivalently $|\beta| \leq 2$ with $\beta = \alpha\hat{\kappa}e^{ik\Delta x} + \alpha\kappa e^{-iK\Delta X} - 2(\alpha\bar{\kappa} - 1)$. Rewriting β in the complex form gives

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re}(\beta) &= \alpha\hat{\kappa} \cos(k\Delta x) + \alpha\kappa \cos(-K\Delta X) - 2(\alpha\bar{\kappa} - 1), \\ \text{Im}(\beta) &= \alpha\hat{\kappa} \sin(k\Delta x) + \alpha\kappa \sin(-K\Delta X), \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

and the stability criterion is $[\text{Re}(\beta)]^2 + [\text{Im}(\beta)]^2 \leq 4$. In the complex plane β , the stability criterion draws a circle of radius $|\beta| \leq 2$ with $\beta = (\text{Re}(\beta), \text{Im}(\beta))$. Note that the stability limit restricts the combination of material parameters of both models, their spatial discretization steps, propagating wave wavenumber, density of the coupling cell and the time step. Hence, for a selected set of material and space discretization parameters, the critical time step $\hat{\Delta}t$ can be computed.

The complex number β , given by Eq. (22), can be interpreted as a combination of two vectors $\mathbf{x} = \alpha\hat{\kappa}e^{+ik\Delta x}$ and $\mathbf{X} = \alpha\kappa e^{-iK\Delta X}$ of respective lengths $\alpha\hat{\kappa}$ and $\alpha\kappa$. Note that the vectors rotate counterclockwise and clockwise, respectively, when k and K increase and their rotation speeds are proportional to element sizes in the coupled domains. Since α , κ and $\hat{\kappa}$ do not depend on the wavenumber, the worst respective configuration of vectors, i.e. largest value of $[\text{Re}(\beta)]^2 + [\text{Im}(\beta)]^2$ — determining the stability — is given by their co-linear configuration, namely $k\Delta x + K\Delta X = 2\pi n$, for n being an integer number, $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). Note this general relationship depends explicitly on element sizes in both domains and implicitly on other model and material parameters — involved in the dispersion relation (and, thus, present in k and K). It is clear, therefore, that the stability will largely depend on the relation between Δx and ΔX . Figure 4(b) illustrates three specific configurations of vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{X} . In (I) and (II) both vectors are close to the $\text{Re}(\beta)$ axis. For (I) $k\Delta x \approx K\Delta X \approx 0$ (the long wavelength limit), while for (II) $k\Delta x \approx K\Delta X \approx \pi$. Obviously, this is the most preferable configuration and if material properties are equal between the models it follows that $\text{Im}(\beta) = 0$. It is, however, possible that element sizes vary significantly (e.g. for spatially multi-scale or multi-resolution analyses). Then, critical combinations of element sizes drive the stability, as shown in Fig. 4(b) by (III). Here, $K\Delta X \approx 3k\Delta x$, i.e. \mathbf{x} rotates three times slower than \mathbf{X} to add co-linearly. These interpretations and findings will be used later on for analysis of more complex coupling scenarios.

Fig. 4. Vector interpretation of Eq. (22) as two oppositely rotating vectors, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{X} . For certain combinations of rotation speeds, Δx and ΔX , vectors add co-linearly (a). Maximum magnitude of β can be obtained for various relative rotational speeds $\Delta x/\Delta X$ (b).

Before proceeding to a more detailed analysis, a crude stability estimate can be given assuming that spatial discretizations do not differ significantly between the models and the material contrast, $\bar{\kappa}$, is not high. Then, the worst case of the complex valued β parameter is

$$\text{Re}(\beta) = 2 - 4\alpha\bar{\kappa}, \quad \text{Im}(\beta) = 2\alpha\bar{\kappa}. \quad (23)$$

Consequently, the stability condition yields $\alpha\bar{\kappa} \in (0, 0.8]$.

A more precise estimate is found by analyzing the interdependent linear and trigonometric functions in Eq. (22) (i.e. relative rotations of \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{X}). Details are given in subsequent sections. Let

$$\alpha\hat{\kappa} = \frac{\bar{E}/\rho^b}{\Delta x^2/\Delta t^2} = \frac{v^2}{v_m^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha\kappa = \frac{E^B/\rho^b}{\Delta x\Delta X/\Delta t^2} = \frac{\bar{v}^2}{\bar{v}_m^2}, \quad (24)$$

and

$$\Omega = \begin{cases} \alpha\hat{\kappa} & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \alpha\kappa & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x, \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \Gamma = \begin{cases} \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta X} & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \frac{\Delta X}{\Delta x} & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x, \end{cases} \quad \Gamma \leq 1, \quad (25)$$

where

$$v^2 = \frac{\bar{E}}{\rho^b}, \quad \bar{v}^2 = \frac{E^B}{\rho^b}, \quad v_m^2 = \frac{\Delta x^2}{\Delta t^2}, \quad \bar{v}_m^2 = \frac{\Delta x\Delta X}{\Delta t^2}, \quad (26)$$

and

$$V^2 = \frac{E^B}{\rho} \quad \text{and} \quad V_m^2 = \frac{\Delta X^2}{\Delta t^2}. \quad (27)$$

In Eqs. (24)–(27):

- v_m and v refer to the model velocity and velocity of wave propagation in the CAFE domain, respectively, and the term $\alpha\hat{\kappa}$ relates to the stability of CAFE domain;
- \bar{v}_m and \bar{v} refer to the model velocity and velocity of wave propagation in the coupling (interface) domain, respectively, and the factor $\alpha\kappa$ relates to the stability of the interface region;
- V_m and V denote the model velocity and velocity of wave propagation in the LISA domain, respectively, and V^2/V_m^2 ratio relates to the stability of LISA domain.

The above notation can be used to intuitively express the stability conditions for the 1D coupled system as the ratio of wave propagation velocity to the model velocity to be less than 1 for a stable solution, with 1 being the stability limit [Delsanto *et al.* (1992)]. Note that for stability, both the LISA and CAFE, and their coupled node need to be individually stable. Also, in order for the coupling to be efficient, we require that the critical time step of the coupled (interface) node is not smaller than the smaller of the LISA or CAFE critical time steps. This ensures that the coupling would not introduce additional limitations to the model

efficiency. Note that the stability of LISA is given by the ratio V^2/V_m^2 , CAFE by $v^2/v_m^2 = \alpha\hat{\kappa}$ and the coupled node by $\bar{v}^2/\bar{v}_m^2 = \alpha\kappa$, then Eq. (22) can be used to analyze critical combinations of $k\Delta x$ and $k\Delta X$ related to extreme points of $\text{Re}(\beta)^2 + \text{Im}(\beta)^2$. In the following sections, we analyze particular cases of model parameters combinations and employ vector-based analysis in the β space to facilitate finding stability conditions.

4.1. No restrictions on coupled models' parameters

We start by an idealized case for which all models satisfy $\Omega = \alpha\hat{\kappa} = \alpha\kappa = V^2/V_m^2$. As a consequence discretization parameters and physical constants are selected in order to obtain largest possible critical time step. With the above definition of Ω and from (24), we have

$$\frac{\bar{E}}{E^B} = \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta X} = \frac{\rho}{\rho^b}. \quad (28)$$

Note that in particular, Eq. (28) does not imply equal element sizes for the coupled domains. For analyzing stability, we first select a combination of material properties and spatial discretization parameters, followed by selecting time step Δt in order to keep the desired value of Ω . With the above assumption, constant values of Ω mark (circular) wavenumber-dependent contours in the β space with the contour value related to the stability. In what follows, we assume the critical time step is the upper bound for all wavenumbers. Then, the stability limit is given by $\Omega = 1$ for which the model will be stable for wave of any wavenumber (or, equivalently, frequency). Selecting model parameters resulting in $\Omega \leq 1$ would lead to stable models, and having $\Omega > 1$ would indicate instability, as shown in Fig. 5(a) (note the range of parameters for stable models is grayed out). Note that for the $\Omega = 1$ contour, the selected time step value is the critical time step $\hat{\Delta t}$.

The predicted stability region is numerically validated by running dynamic transient simulations for a set of models. Circle and square markers denote numerical model setups resulting in stable and unstable solutions, respectively. It can be clearly seen from Fig. 5(a) that dynamic transient simulations confirm the predicted range of model parameters resulting in stable solutions. Using $\Omega = \alpha\hat{\kappa} = \alpha\kappa = V^2/V_m^2$ and Eq. (22) and re-arrangement, the contours shown in Fig. 5(a) are given by

$$\beta = \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} + \Omega e^{-iK\Delta X} - 2(\Omega - 1). \quad (29)$$

Clearly, $\mathbf{x} = \Omega e^{ik\Delta x}$ and $\mathbf{X} = \Omega e^{-iK\Delta X}$ are vectors of length Ω in the β plane, that rotate counterclockwise and clockwise, respectively, when k and K increase. As noted before, the worst respective configuration of vectors is their co-linear arrangement, i.e. $k\Delta x + K\Delta X = 2\pi n$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Using this condition, we get $\mathbf{X} = \Omega e^{k\Delta x}$ and Eq. (29) yields

$$\beta = 2\Omega e^{ik\Delta x} + 2 - 2\Omega. \quad (30)$$

Fig. 5. Space of numerical model parameters for stability analysis. (a) The stability circle with various constant- Ω contours for $\Omega = \alpha\kappa = \alpha\kappa = V^2/V_m^2$. (b) Contours for three model configurations — no restrictions on coupled models' parameters, equal stiffnesses, and equal stiffnesses and densities in both the models — at the stability limit. The stability space shrinks for equal stiffness in both domains, and when all material parameters are equal. Circle and square markers indicate combinations of model parameters for stable and unstable dynamic transient simulations, respectively. Arrows indicate increasing Γ in upper half and decreasing Γ in the lower half.

In this form, the circle of radius 2Ω marked by increasing k can be clearly identified. The center of the circle is located at $(2 - 2\Omega, 0)$ in the β plane. This finding is immediately seen in Fig. 5(a) for various values of Ω . In Fig. 5(a), four characteristic points on the stability circle were marked by A, B, C and D — representing four (exemplary) configurations of a numerical model. These points represent extreme values of purely real β (points B and D) and purely imaginary β (points A and C).

At points B and D, we have $k\Delta x = -K\Delta X + 2\pi n = 0$ and $k\Delta x = -K\Delta X + 2\pi n = \pi$, respectively. With $n = 0$, points B and D refer to the same element sizes in both domains and two limiting values, namely the long wavelength limit, $k, K \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta x = \Delta X \rightarrow \lambda/2$ — the Brillouin zone edge (the short wavelength limit). For $n = 0$ and together with the definition of Ω it follows that for those points Young's moduli and densities remain the same in both domains. The same points can be reached in the β space for $n \neq 0$, i.e. for element sizes of different lengths, and require proper adjustment of other material constants.

The line B–D is obtained for $\sin(k\Delta x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow k = n\pi/\Delta x, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (see Eq. (30)). Due to discretization and the resulting spatial aliasing, the only solution is $k \rightarrow 0$, so the long wavelength limit. The B–D line is approached for element sizes sufficiently small compared to the wavelength and for $\Delta x = \Delta X$.

Reaching points A and C requires nonzero (extreme) imaginary part of β , thus significantly different Δx and ΔX . Substantial difference in element sizes is compensated by properly adjusted material constants values at A and C. These configurations are, however, not practical and require drastic material contrasts in order to fully exploit stability space. When material parameters are required the same

or similar between the domains, additional constraints are imposed on the model. Therefore, stability space reduces, as shown next.

4.2. Equal Young's moduli

It is of practical importance to analyze a special case of a model where the stiffness constants (i.e. Young moduli) in LISA and CAFE are equal. Such a scenario will arise in a multi-scale model with nominally the same physical stiffness properties, but using LISA and CAFE in different parts of the domain (e.g. different at a crack and for the body of the structure). Note that in this case $\alpha\hat{\kappa} \neq \alpha\kappa \neq V^2/V_m^2$ and the stability space will reduce. Therefore, the stability of the coupled model will be driven by individual stability properties of different models in the upper ($\text{Im}(\beta) > 0$) and lower ($\text{Im}(\beta) < 0$) half-planes of the β space (see Eq. (29)). In the upper half, i.e., CAFE-driven, we assume $\alpha\hat{\kappa} = 1$, $\alpha\kappa < 1$ and $V^2/V_m^2 < 1$ while in the lower-half — driven by LISA and the coupled node — we assume $\alpha\kappa = 1$, $V^2/V_m^2 = 1$ and $\alpha\hat{\kappa} < 1$. With this particular choice, the circular contours reduce to an asymmetric shape, as shown in Fig. 5(b) for the stability limit for the least stable model. Clearly, it follows from Fig. 5(b) that the space of stable model parameters is substantially reduced when requiring equal stiffness constants in the coupled models.

With equal stiffness constants (Young's moduli) in LISA and CAFE, Eq. (29) changes for the upper and lower halves in the following way (note the definition of Ω given by Eq. (25))

$$\beta = \begin{cases} \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} + \Gamma \Omega e^{-iK\Delta X} - 2(\bar{\Omega} - 1) & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \Gamma \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} + \Omega e^{-iK\Delta X} - 2(\bar{\Omega} - 1) & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x, \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

where $\bar{\Omega} = \frac{\Omega + \Gamma\Omega}{2}$. Equation (31) implies deformation of the stability circle due to the Γ factor. Recalling that $\Gamma \leq 1$ (see Eq. (25)), values of Ω from Eq. (31) may theoretically exceed 1 and still $|\beta| \leq 2$. This effect can be clearly seen by considering a limiting case of $\Delta X \gg \Delta x$, i.e., $\Gamma \ll 1$. Then, Eq. (31) for the upper half yields $\text{Re}(\beta) \approx \Omega \cos(k\Delta x) - \Omega + 2$ and $\text{Im}(\beta) \approx \Omega \sin(k\Delta x)$, with the stability given by $\text{Re}^2(\beta) + \text{Im}^2(\beta) - 4 = 2\Omega(1 - \cos(k\Delta x))(\Omega - 2) \leq 0$ and satisfied by $\Omega \in \langle 0, 2 \rangle$. Since solutions with $\Omega > 1$ are unstable, the allowable time step needs to be reduced when compared to the unconstrained case, effectively shrinking the space of stable solutions as shown in Fig. 5(b). Please also note the symmetry in $\text{Im}(\beta)$ in Eq. (31) and the consequent symmetry of the stability space with respect to the horizontal axis of Fig. 5(b).

The vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{X} can be written as

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{cases} \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \Gamma \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x, \end{cases}$$

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{cases} \Gamma \Omega e^{-iK\Delta X} & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \Omega e^{-iK\Delta X} & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x. \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

The worst respective configuration of vectors, i.e. largest value of $[\text{Re}(\beta)]^2 + [\text{Im}(\beta)]^2$ — determining the stability — is given by their co-linear configuration, namely $k\Delta x + K\Delta X = 2\pi n$. Using this condition, Eq. (31) yields

$$\beta = (1 + \Gamma)\Omega e^{ik\Delta x} - 2(\overline{\Omega} - 1), \quad (33)$$

which resembles the form of the Archimedean spiral (note that Ω is a constant since ρ^b can compensate for the change in Δx , and Γ is linear in Δx in the upper half and in ΔX in the lower half). Equation (33), defines the worst model configurations and encloses the stability space for a coupled model with equal stiffness parameters. The shape of the stability space for this model is shown in Fig. 5(b).

It can be observed that for equal stiffnesses of the models and at the stability limit, the space of stable model parameters reduces. As for the previous case, we run a set of numerical models to validate this estimate for stability of the coupled numerical scheme. Similarly, circle and square markers are used to indicate stable and unstable solutions, respectively. It can be seen from Fig. 5(b) that dynamic transient simulations confirm the predicted range of model parameters resulting in stable solutions.

4.3. Equal Young's moduli and equal densities

We finally analyze the case of equal stiffnesses and densities of the two coupled models. Such a set of model parameters would be the most simple choice when setting up a numerical simulation, leaving element sizes as the only variables.

As in the previous case (equal Young's moduli) we have $\alpha\hat{\kappa} \neq \alpha\kappa \neq V^2/V_m^2$, and the stability of the coupled model will be driven by individual stability properties of the two coupled models. Here, the upper half — as previously — is CAFE-driven, however, the lower half is only LISA-driven (unlike in the previous case where the lower half was driven by both LISA and the coupled node). This further changes the lower half of the stability space such that $\alpha\hat{\kappa}$ and $\alpha\kappa$ change by a factor of Γ . With these assumptions Eq. (31) remains same for the upper half, but changes for the lower half in the following way (note the definition of Ω given by Eq. (25) and the absence of LISA's density in Ω)

$$\beta = \begin{cases} \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} + \Gamma\Omega e^{-iK\Delta X} - 2(\overline{\Omega} - 1) & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \Gamma^2\Omega e^{ik\Delta x} + \Gamma\Omega e^{-iK\Delta X} - 2(\Gamma\overline{\Omega} - 1) & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x. \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

The equations are different for the two cases, resulting in asymmetric stability space because the density of LISA, ρ , does not appear in Eq. (22). When equal densities are considered in the two domains, compensation for the change in Γ (cell lengths ratio) is no longer possible for $\Delta x > \Delta X$ (i.e., the density cannot fully compensate for CAFE's cell length Δx), but this ability is still retained for $\Delta X > \Delta x$ (the density can fully compensate for CAFE's cell length, Δx). If CAFE's cell length is fully compensated by the density, then $V^2/V_m^2 > 1$ (LISA's stability condition), resulting in LISA and — in consequence — the coupled model to be unstable.

This inability of the density to fully compensate for CAFE’s cell length, Δx , is reflected by the stability curve been shrunk in the lower half. When $\Delta X > \Delta x$, the density parameter cannot fully compensate for LISA’s cell length, ΔX , but it can fully compensate for CAFE’s cell length, Δx . The density of the LISA domain, ρ , potentially capable of compensating for ΔX does not appear in the stability equations. In that case, the time step must be further reduced as reflected in the lower half of the stability plane. As a result of these model-dependent configurations, the stability space assumes an asymmetric shape as shown in Fig. 5(b).

The vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{X} for the case of equal Young’s moduli and densities can be written as

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{cases} \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \Gamma^2 \Omega e^{ik\Delta x} & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x, \end{cases}$$

$$\mathbf{X} = \Gamma \Omega e^{-iK\Delta X}. \tag{35}$$

While the worst (co-linear) respective configuration of vectors gives

$$\beta = \begin{cases} (1 + \Gamma)\Omega e^{ik\Delta x} - 2(\Gamma\bar{\Omega} - 1) & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \Gamma(1 + \Gamma)\Omega e^{ik\Delta x} - 2(\Gamma\bar{\Omega} - 1) & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x. \end{cases} \tag{36}$$

Analogously to the previous sections, a set of numerical simulations was run in order to confirm the shape of the stability space, as shown in Fig. 5(b) by markers. Further validation is reported in the following section.

4.4. Discussion

As noted in Sec. 4, the coupled model stability depends on three conditions: stability of the LISA, CAFE and the coupled node. Each individual model stability is related to the critical time step given as

$$\Delta t_{\text{LISA}} = \frac{\Delta X^2}{E^B/\rho}, \quad \Delta t_{\text{CAFE}} = \frac{\Delta x^2}{E/\rho^b}, \quad \Delta t_{\text{CPL}} = \frac{\Delta x \Delta X}{E^B/\rho^b}, \tag{37}$$

where the smallest of time steps in (37) will determine the stability of the coupled model.

Assuming first $\bar{E} = E^B$ and $\rho = \rho^b$, i.e., the case of Sec. 4.3, the normalized critical time steps are given by

$$\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{LISA}} = \Delta t_{\text{LISA}} E^B/\rho = \Delta X^2, \quad \Delta \bar{t}_{\text{CAFE}} = \Delta t_{\text{CAFE}} \bar{E}/\rho^b = \Delta x^2, \tag{38}$$

$$\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{CPL}} = \Delta t_{\text{CPL}} E^B/\rho^b = \Delta x \Delta X.$$

Then, clearly

$$\Delta X \leq \Delta x : \Delta \bar{t}_{\text{LISA}} \leq \Delta \bar{t}_{\text{CPL}} \leq \Delta \bar{t}_{\text{CAFE}}, \tag{39}$$

meaning that the determining parameters for the critical time step in the upper ($\Delta X \geq \Delta x$) and lower ($\Delta X < \Delta x$) parts of the stability plane are $\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{CAFE}}$

and $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{LISA}}$, respectively. Consequently, the stability space assumes an asymmetric shape.

When considering the case of Sec. 4.2, i.e., $\bar{E} = E^B$, the normalized critical time steps take the form

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{LISA}} &= \Delta t_{\text{LISA}} E^B = \Delta X^2 \rho, & \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CAFE}} &= \Delta t_{\text{CAFE}} \bar{E} = \Delta x^2 \rho^b, \\ \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CPL}} &= \Delta t_{\text{CPL}} E^B = \Delta x \Delta X \rho^b, \end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

and

$$\Delta X \leq \Delta x : \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CPL}} \leq \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CAFE}} \leq \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{LISA}}(\rho). \tag{41}$$

In Eq. (41) for $\Delta X < \Delta x$ the determining parameter is $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CPL}}$, while for $\Delta X \geq \Delta x$ the stability is governed by $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CAFE}}$. The reason for this is that after fixing ΔX and Δx , the critical time steps for CAFE and the coupled domain involve the same value of density ρ^b . In result one of these time steps will drive the stability, while the critical time step for LISA, $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{LISA}}(\rho)$, can be made sufficiently large by properly adjusting ρ . This is not possible when the LISA density, ρ , is required to be equal to ρ^b , as in the previous case. In particular, if ρ is selected so $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CPL}} = \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{LISA}}$, then $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CAFE}} = \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{CPL}}$ and the stability contour is symmetric.

In the most general case of Sec. 4.1, all parameters (i.e., \bar{E} , E^B , ρ^b and ρ) can be used to compensate for differences in ΔX and Δx , so the only condition restricting stability is $|\beta| \leq 2$.

5. Stability Analysis of the Coupled Scheme in 2D

Unlike the 1D stability space affected by Δx , ΔX , material properties and the time step, the 2D stability space is further influenced by vertical cell discretization parameters Δy and ΔY . The added dimension of cell discretization and the added elastic moduli provide extra degrees of freedom for stability in the 2D case. This section discusses how different combinations of these added parameters affect the stability space. In 2D, each domain will be associated with a wavenumber — $\mathbf{K} = (K_X, K_Y)$ for LISA and $\mathbf{k} = (k_x, k_y)$ for CAFE.

Analogously to the 1D case, the influence of $k_x \Delta x$ and $K_X \Delta X$ in 2D is additive and results in a (green) circle in the β plane, as seen in Fig. 6(a). Contributions of $k_y \Delta y$ and $K_Y \Delta Y$ are ellipsoidal, i.e., are coupled and not additive. In that coupled effect, $k_y \Delta y$ affects the inner radius of the ellipsoidal shape while $K_Y \Delta Y$ — its thickness (see Fig. 6(b)). In analysis that follows, we introduce the ratio $\eta = \Delta x / \Delta y$ to distinguish different determining parameters — if $\eta > 1$, the ellipsoidal's influence is greater than the circles and as it increases, the circles become smaller. For $\eta < 1$, the influence of $k_y \Delta y$ and $K_Y \Delta Y$ is smaller than that of $k_x \Delta x$ and $K_X \Delta X$, and subsequently, the influence of the circles is greater than the ellipse, and as η decreases the circles become larger. Figure 6(b) shows an example when Δx is significantly greater than Δy — the circles are small and the stability space is influenced predominantly by the ellipse. It can be also observed that the case when

Fig. 6. (a) Influence of combinations $k_x \Delta x$ and $K_X \Delta X$, and $k_y \Delta y$ and $K_Y \Delta Y$ on the stability space — leading to circular and ellipsoidal shapes, respectively. (b) Influence of $\eta = \Delta x / \Delta y$ on the stability space.

Δx is significantly smaller than Δy , the stability space is influenced predominately by the circle. The latter is analogous to the 1D case. In the following sections, we demonstrate results for a 2D system for $\eta = \{1/5, 1, 5\}$ and explore analogies to the 1D case.

5.1. No restrictions on coupled models' parameters

We start with an idealized case wherein the discretization parameters and physical constants of the multi-scale model are selected to obtain largest possible time step, i.e., material properties may be changed (are not constrained) to compensate for different discretization lengths to exploit the whole stability space. From the individual stability conditions of LISA and CAFE, and without loss of generality assuming $\lambda = 2\mu$ to simplify the analysis, we have $\alpha_C \mu_C = \alpha_L \mu_L$ at the stability limit ($\alpha_C = \alpha = \frac{\Delta t^2}{\rho_C \Delta x \Delta y}$ and $\alpha_L = \frac{\Delta t^2}{\rho_L \Delta X \Delta Y}$). Then, the following relation holds:

$$\frac{\mu_C}{\mu_L} \frac{\rho_L}{\rho_C} = \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta X} \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta Y} \Leftrightarrow \frac{\mu_C}{\mu_L} = \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta X}, \quad \frac{\rho_L}{\rho_C} = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta Y}. \quad (42)$$

The decomposition in Eq. (42) may be arbitrary, but since ρ_L does not appear in the coupling equation it may be used to compensate for the constraint dimension of $\Delta Y = \Delta y$. Figure 7(a) illustrates stability contours for various values of η . For $\eta < 1$, Δx is the dominating factor and the stability space gradually transforms into a circle (see Fig. 7(b)). Δy does not play a critical role in this case and the β space is analogous to the 1D setup. When η increases and for $\eta > 1$, Δy becomes the dominating factor and the stability contour deforms into an ellipse (see Fig. 7(c)). This shape is driven by $k_y \Delta Y$ and $K_Y \Delta Y$, especially for $\eta \gg 1$, as seen in Figs. 7(a) and 7(d). For that case, Δx plays secondary role for stability. The stability contours of Fig. 7(a) correspond to the extreme critical time step values and employ material properties as parameters that can be adjusted to compensate changes in Δx and

Fig. 7. Space of numerical model parameters for stability analysis in 2D. (a) The stability circle with contours representing stability limits for different η . (b)–(d) Illustrate contours for two model configurations: no restrictions on coupled models’ parameters and equal material properties (stiffness constants and densities) in both domains for $\eta = 1/5$ (b), $\eta = 1$ (c) and $\eta = 5$ (d). Clearly, the space of stable solutions shrinks when restrictions are imposed in both the models. Circle and square markers indicate combinations of model parameters for stable and unstable dynamic transient simulations, respectively. Arrows indicate increasing Γ in upper half and decreasing Γ in the lower half.

ΔX . In the intermediate case of $\eta = 1$, the stability contour resembles the circle more than the ellipse, indicating the dominant impact of $k_x \Delta x$ and $K_X \Delta X$ over $k_y \Delta Y$ and $K_Y \Delta Y$.

Using the relations discussed above, the contours shown in Fig. 7(a) and the not restricted contours in Figs. 7(b)–7(d) are given by

$$\beta = \hat{\Omega} e^{ik_x \Delta x} \left(5\eta + \frac{5}{2}\eta^3 + \frac{3}{2}\eta^3 e^{-2ik_x \Delta x} \right) - \hat{\Omega}(5\eta + 4\eta^3) - \bar{\psi}_R - \bar{\psi}_I + 2, \quad (43)$$

where $\bar{\psi}_R = \hat{\Omega} \frac{\psi_R}{\Delta y^2}$ and $\bar{\psi}_I = i\hat{\Omega} \frac{\psi_I}{\Delta y^2}$ with $\hat{\Omega} = \frac{\Delta t^2 \mu_C}{\eta \Delta x^2 \rho_C}$, and ψ_R and ψ_I are nonlinear terms that are functions of cell discretization lengths, elastic constants and the phase angle. The maximum value of $\hat{\Omega}$ represents the stability limit of the coupled model at a particular η and for $\eta = \{1/5, 1, 5\}$, the maximum value of $\hat{\Omega} = \{1.23, 0.2, 0.002\}$.

It can be observed from Fig. 7(a) that at $\eta \approx 1$ the stability space does not occupy the full circle, and as η becomes larger than 1, the stability space shrinks. For each contour in Fig. 7(a) the respective $\hat{\Omega}$ relates to the critical time step.

An estimate of the stability condition for same material properties and spatial discretization lengths in the models, i.e., $\mu_C = \mu_L = \mu$, $\lambda_C = \lambda_L = \lambda$, $\rho_C = \rho_L = \rho$, $\Delta X = \Delta x = \Delta Y = \Delta y$, in Eq. (43) gives

$$\Delta t^2 \leq \frac{\Delta x^2 \rho}{(\lambda + 2\mu) + \mu} \Leftrightarrow \frac{V^2}{V_M^2} \leq 1 \Leftrightarrow V_M \geq \sqrt{V_L^2 + V_T^2}, \quad (44)$$

where V and V_M represent the velocity of wave propagation and the model velocity, respectively, and $\lambda + 2\mu = \rho V_L^2$, $\mu = \rho V_T^2$, where V_L and V_T are the longitudinal and shear wave velocities, respectively. Equation (44) recovers the well-known CFL condition [Delsanto *et al.* (1994)].

5.2. Equal stiffness constants and densities

Based on the decomposition of Eq. (42), the relation governing the densities of LISA and CAFE yields $\rho_C = \rho_L$, i.e., equal densities in the coupled domains. Thus, the scenario of equal stiffness constants and unequal densities cannot be explored as in the 1D case (Sec. 4.2). The stability then, like in the 1D case, is driven by CAFE in the upper half ($\Delta X > \Delta x$) and LISA in the lower half ($\Delta X < \Delta x$). Then, for $\lambda = 2\mu$, Eq. (43) changes for the upper and lower halves in the following way:

$$\beta = \begin{cases} \hat{\Omega} e^{ik_x \Delta x} \left(\frac{5}{2} \eta (1 + \Gamma) + \frac{5}{2} \eta^3 + \frac{3}{2} \eta^3 e^{-2ik_x \Delta x} \right) \\ \quad - \hat{\Omega} \left(\frac{5}{2} \eta (1 + \Gamma) + 4\eta^3 \right) - \bar{\bar{\psi}}_R - \bar{\bar{\psi}}_I + 2 & \text{for } \Delta X \geq \Delta x, \\ \nu \hat{\Omega} e^{ik_x \Delta x} \left(\frac{5}{2} \eta (1 + \Gamma) + \frac{5}{2} \eta^3 + \frac{3}{2} \eta^3 e^{-2ik_x \Delta x} \right) \\ \quad - \nu \hat{\Omega} \left(\frac{5}{2} \eta (1 + \Gamma) + 4\eta^3 \right) - \bar{\bar{\psi}}_R - \bar{\bar{\psi}}_I + 2 & \text{for } \Delta X < \Delta x, \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

where $\bar{\bar{\psi}}_R = \hat{\Omega} \frac{\Gamma \hat{\psi}_R}{\Delta y^2}$ and $\bar{\bar{\psi}}_I = i \hat{\Omega} \frac{\Gamma \hat{\psi}_I}{\Delta y^2}$, and $\hat{\psi}_R$ and $\hat{\psi}_I$ are nonlinear functions of cell discretization lengths and the phase angle. Like in the 1D case $\Gamma = \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta X}$ (Eq. (25)) and ν is a nonlinear factor which is a function of Γ .

As illustrated in Figs. 7(b)–7(d) and analogously to the 1D case, the stability space shrinks when the restriction of equal material properties is imposed. The upper and lower half contours are asymmetric because the density of LISA (ρ_L) does not appear in the coupling equations as discussed in Sec. 4.3. It can be observed that for $\eta = 5$ the shrinkage is hardly visible. This happens because for $\eta = 5$, Δy is dominating the stability more than Δx and ΔX , thus, Γ appearing in Eq. (45) becomes less significant. However, in the lower half, owing to ν the shrinkage effect is slightly visible.

5.3. Discussion

In the 2D case, as more degrees of freedom to manipulate stability are present, the contours in the β space are more complex. Congruent meshes at the interface impose $\Delta y = \Delta Y$ constraint affecting the analysis. The stability space strongly depends on the value η — representative of the 2D model similarity to the 1D case. In particular for $\eta \ll 1$ the full stability space can be exploited. Such a case is, however, not of high practical interest as is $\eta \approx 1$. In that latter situation, the stability space is naturally reduced. Figures 7(b)–7(d) illustrate deformations of the stability space for various constraints imposed in the models.

6. Numerical Validation

Previous sections report analysis results for the coupled models equations, Eq. (18) (1D) and Eq. (20) (2D). Consequently, stability spaces shown in Figs. 5 and 6 show model configurations, i.e., the sets of material and discretization parameters (including the time step Δt), that result in stable solutions. In this section, results presented earlier for both 1D and 2D cases are validated using dynamic transient simulations.

Each set of material and discretization parameters defining a model is represented by a point in the β space according to Eq. (22) (1D) and Eq. (43) (2D). Also, for all selected model parameters, a change in the time step value results in a shift in the β space along a line passing through $\beta = (2, 0)$ since Ω and $\hat{\Omega}$ are proportional to Δt^2 (thus $|\beta| \propto \Delta t$), and they appear linearly in Eqs. (29) and (43), respectively. For $\Delta t = 0 \Leftrightarrow \beta = (2, 0)$, and while increasing the time step size a point in the β space moves along a line as shown in Fig. 8 for two model setups β_i and β_{i+1} where $\Delta t_i < \Delta t_{i+1}$.

Fig. 8. (a) Example Δt -dependent paths in the β space. Points on the same line differ by the time step value Δt . (b) Comparison of analytically predicted contours (lines) with critical values of β points obtained from numerical simulations (markers) for all three conditions (no restrictions, equal Young’s moduli, and equal Young’s moduli and equal densities).

Dynamic transient simulations were performed for selected combinations of material properties and spatial discretization parameters. For the 1D case, each domain, i.e., LISA and CAFE, was considered to be 2m long with the number of elements defined by the ratio of domain length to spatial discretization size. The noncoupled boundaries of LISA and CAFE were assumed to be stress-free. The excitation was applied at the left-hand side of the simulation domain (i.e., the LISA domain) as a narrowband wave packet at half of the cut-off frequency (for the specified discretization parameters) with 100 sine periods shaped by half-Hann windowing of the first and last 20 wave periods. The wave packet was generated in the time domain and applied to the simulation domain (LISA domain) at every time step as prescribed displacement.

For the 2D case, LISA and CAFE domains were considered 80×80 mm each with the number of elements in the horizontal and vertical directions defined by the respective spatial discretizations (ΔX , Δx and $\Delta Y = \Delta y$). The noncoupled boundaries of LISA and CAFE were assumed to be stress-free. Excitation was a point source displacement applied in the horizontal direction at the center of the LISA domain as a wave packet at half of the cut-off frequency (for the specified discretization) with 2 sine periods shaped by Hann windowing. This wave packet, like in the 1D case, was generated in the time domain and applied in the LISA domain at every time step as prescribed displacement.

For both the 1D and 2D validation, the number of time steps was adjusted accordingly to match 20s of real time. To evaluate the stability of the coupled model, displacements in both domains were checked at each time instant. The model was considered unstable when the largest displacement magnitude in the model exceeded 10^{20} . Examples of a stable and unstable simulation results for the 1D case are shown in Figs. 10(a) and 10(b), respectively, and for the 2D case are shown in Figs. 10(c) and 10(e), respectively. An interesting observation can be made from Fig. 10(a) (see the left-hand side and the inset), where a narrowband wave packet was used as excitation. The wave packet traveling from left to right was partially transmitted (blue line on the right-hand side, traveling to the right) and partially reflected (orange line on the left-hand side, traveling to the left). In this particular case, the reflected wave amplitude reaches approximately 10% of the incident wave. The reason for this artificial reflection is the impedance mismatch between the domains due to different material and discretization parameters (note the reflection may remain nonzero even for equal material properties). A similar case of artificial reflection can also be observed for the 2D case in Fig. 10(c). In Fig. 10(e), which shows an inset of Fig. 10(c) for all the nodes in the horizontal direction at $Y = 40$ mm, artificial reflection owing to impedance mismatch between the two domains can be clearly seen near the coupling region. As artificial reflections are of particular interest for accuracy of a numerical model, their detailed analysis is a topic of follow-up work.

In total, for the 1D case, 118 models were run for all three model setups outlined in Secs. 4.1–4.3, i.e., for no constraints on model parameters, for equal Young's

Fig. 9. Comparison of analytically predicted contours (lines) with critical values in the β space obtained from numerical simulations (markers): (a) for no restrictions on coupled models' parameters model configuration and (b) for equal material properties in the coupled models, for $\eta = \{1/5, 1, 5\}$.

moduli, and for equal Young's moduli and equal densities, while for the 2D case, 500 models were run for all model setups outlined in Secs. 5.1 and 5.2, i.e., for unconstrained and constrained model parameters at $\eta = \{1/5, 1, 5\}$. In each simulation, the time step was initially set to $\Delta t = 0.05$ and increased gradually with an increment of 0.01 until the critical time step, $\Delta \hat{t}$, was reached (i.e., the model

Fig. 10. Views of the 1D and 2D coupled model for a selected time instant. (a) Stable simulation (1D case) results show numerical reflections from the coupling region owing to impedance mismatch between the two domains due to different discretization parameters. (b) An unstable simulation (1D case) owing to the model parameters and time step resulting in a point that falls outside the stable region (see Fig. 5). (c) Stable simulation (2D case) results show numerical reflections from the coupling region owing to impedance mismatch between the two domains due to different discretization parameters. (d) An unstable simulation (2D case) owing to the model parameters and time step resulting in a point that falls outside the stable region (see Fig. 7). (e) An inset of Fig. 10(c) for all the nodes in the horizontal direction at $Y = 40$ mm shows numerical reflections from the coupling region.

Fig. 10. (Continued)

was unstable). The time step values corresponding to the first unstable model configurations were used to determine shapes of stability spaces through numerical experiments. Results obtained from 1D and 2D simulations are shown in Figs. 8(b) and 9 (markers), respectively, along with analytically predicted contours (lines). It can be seen that perfect agreement was obtained.

6.1. Increasing the critical time step

Finally, conclusions from the stability analysis are employed for maximizing efficiency of the multi-scale model. The latter is achieved through increasing time step of the analysis by altering material properties of the models according to Eq. (42). A set of dynamic transient simulations was run and the largest time step resulting in a stable simulation, $\Delta \hat{t}$, was recorded.

Figure 11 illustrates results from three sets of numerical experiments for a standard and two modified models. In the standard case, all material constants and discretization parameters apart from ΔX and Δx are taken equal and fixed in both domains. When evaluating models, Δx was fixed, while ΔX was changed and

Fig. 11. Results for maximizing efficiency of the multi-scale model through increasing the largest time step of the analysis for three sets of numerical experiments: a standard and two modified models. It can be observed that model modifications lead to equal and increased $\Delta \hat{t}$ for all model setups. The larger the differences between element size in the model, the larger the improvement in model performance.

the critical time step for each setup recorded. Clearly, $\Delta \hat{t}$ depends on the model parameters with the smallest time steps required for small element sizes ΔX .

For the first set of modified models, the material constants of LISA were adjusted to compensate for changes in ΔX while keeping the material constants of CAFE fixed such that $\frac{\mu_C}{\mu_L} = \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta X} \Leftrightarrow \mu_L = \mu_C \frac{\Delta X}{\Delta x}$ and ρ_L was selected to maximize $\Delta \hat{t}$. Figure 11 shows that this modification leads to equal critical time steps for all model setups with the critical time step value greater than the maximum $\Delta \hat{t}$ for the standard case. Depending on the discretization contrast, Γ , improvement in $\Delta \hat{t}$ ranges from 47% for $\Gamma = 1$ to 179% for $\Gamma = 0.5$ to approximately 808% for $\Gamma = 0.1$, i.e., the larger the differences between element size in the model, the larger improvement in model performance.

For the second set of modified models, the stiffness constants and densities of LISA and CAFE were halved and doubled, respectively, while keeping the ratio between LISA and CAFE properties the same as in the previous modification. It can be seen from Fig. 11 that this modification leads to further improvement in the critical time steps for all model setups. This increase in critical time step follows Eq. (44), i.e., from altering individual CFL conditions of LISA and CAFE wherein change in material properties is compensated by the change in the critical time step. The critical time step can be further improved by further decreasing and increasing the stiffness constants and densities, respectively, however, such altering of the individual model properties affects the waveform features. Comparing the second modification with the original model shows that for $\Gamma = 0.1$ the critical time step increases by approximately 1715%, for $\Gamma = 0.5$ by 457%, while for $\Gamma = 1$ by 193%.

7. Conclusions

In this work, we analyzed the stability of dynamic transient models obtained by direct coupling of two different numerical approaches leading to a multi-scale strategy. The models were coupled in time and space, resulting in a self-coupling term for the boundary node. This additional term follows from and depends on a coupling scheme adopted. It also impacts the stability of the model since it may be considered as additional stiffness contribution at the interface. Besides the coupling strategy, complete analysis of the scheme was presented and coupling terms explicitly identified.

The stability of the model was analyzed in the complex domain of β parameter. In contrast to a usual case of an explicit time integration scheme, where the stability is given by a single vector in the β space, additional vector — representative of the second model involved in the coupling — appears. These two vectors rotate in the β space (proportionally to the element sizes and wavenumbers of the coupled domains) in opposite directions and their critical combinations drive the stability of the coupled model.

It was found that the stability space is equivalent to that of an uncoupled model only when differences in numerical dispersion properties of the models are compensated by proper adjustment of discretization and material parameters. This often leads to large mismatch of material properties, e.g., when drastically different element sizes are selected, and results in artificial reflections from the interface of the two models. These effects require detailed analysis and are left for follow-up works.

Further, two model configurations of practical interest were investigated, namely, the case of equal elastic constants and the case of equal elastic constants and densities. These configurations are likely to be common choices for material parameters in the coupled domains. It was found that when the selection of parameters is restricted, e.g., stiffness parameters are required to be equal, the stability space shrinks. This reduction of the stability space is related to the parameter Γ , i.e., to the ratio of element sizes in the coupled domains. The space of stable solutions is further reduced when all material parameters are selected equal between the domains. This indicates that for such cases the time step size needs to be adjusted to maintain stability of the coupled model. Also, in that latter case the stability space is asymmetric since one of the model parameters (density of the LISA domain) does not appear in the stability equations.

The above findings contribute to the analysis and development of dynamic multi-scale hybrid models frequently appearing in numerical modeling. Example of physical problems related to this area cover wave interaction with microstructure, defects, acoustic emission and other.

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Appendix A. LISA-2D

Assuming invariance of material distribution along the vertical direction and using the phase relation $Q_{n,m\pm 1} = Q_n e^{\pm i(K_Y \Delta Y)}$, the final 2D LISA iteration equation for a grid point located at the intersection of four adjacent material cells yields

$$Q_n^{t+1} = 2Q_n^t - Q_n^{t-1} + \frac{\Delta t^2}{\rho} [\kappa_R Q_{n+1} - \kappa_M Q_n + \kappa_L Q_{n-1}], \quad (A.1)$$

where $\rho = \frac{\rho^{(1)} + \rho^{(2)} + \rho^{(3)} + \rho^{(4)}}{4}$ represents the (average) density at the intersection of four adjacent material cells, $Q_{n+c_n}^{t+c_t} = [U_{n+c_n,m}^{t+c_t}, V_{n+c_n,m}^{t+c_t}]^T$, $c_t, c_n \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$. Note that due to the phase relation, all the vectors in Eq. (A.1) refer to the m th vertical node (subscript dropped for clarity). κ_L , κ_M and κ_R are populated with stiffness coefficients related to displacements of left (Q_{n-1}), middle (Q_n) and right (Q_{n+1}) vertical group of cells and are given as following:

$$\kappa_M = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{-(\lambda + 2\mu)^{(A,B)}}{\Delta X^2} + \frac{-2\mu^{(A,B)} + \mu^{(A,B)}e^Y + \mu^{(A,B)}e^{-Y}}{2\Delta Y^2} \\ \frac{(-\lambda^{(B)} + \mu^{(B)} + \lambda^{(A)} - \mu^{(A)})e^Y + (-\lambda^{(A)} + \mu^{(A)} + \lambda^{(B)} - \mu^{(B)})e^{-Y}}{4\Delta X \Delta Y} \\ \frac{(\lambda^{(B)} - \mu^{(B)} - \lambda^{(A)} + \mu^{(A)})e^Y + (\lambda^{(A)} - \mu^{(A)} - \lambda^{(B)} + \mu^{(B)})e^{-Y}}{4\Delta X \Delta Y} \\ \frac{-\mu^{(A,B)}}{\Delta X^2} + \frac{-2(\lambda + 2\mu)^{(A,B)} + (\lambda + 2\mu)^{(A,B)}e^Y + (\lambda + 2\mu)^{(A,B)}e^{-Y}}{2\Delta Y^2} \end{array} \right],$$

$$\kappa_R = \left[\begin{array}{cc} \frac{(\lambda + 2\mu)^{(B)}}{\Delta X^2} & \frac{(\lambda + \mu)^{(B)}e^Y + (-\lambda - \mu)^{(B)}e^{-Y}}{4\Delta X \Delta Y} \\ \frac{(\lambda + \mu)^{(B)}e^Y + (-\lambda - \mu)^{(B)}e^{-Y}}{4\Delta X \Delta Y} & \frac{\mu^{(B)}}{\Delta X^2} \end{array} \right],$$

$$\kappa_L = \left[\begin{array}{cc} \frac{(\lambda + 2\mu)^{(A)}}{\Delta X^2} & \frac{(-\lambda - \mu)^{(A)}e^Y + (\lambda + \mu)^{(A)}e^{-Y}}{4\Delta X \Delta Y} \\ \frac{(-\lambda - \mu)^{(A)}e^Y + (\lambda + \mu)^{(A)}e^{-Y}}{4\Delta X \Delta Y} & \frac{\mu^{(A)}}{\Delta X^2} \end{array} \right],$$

where $e^Y = e^{iK_Y \Delta Y}$.

Appendix B. CAFE-2D

Assuming invariance of material distribution along the vertical direction and using the phase relation $q_{n,m\pm 1} = q_n e^{\pm i(k_y \Delta y)}$, the final 2D CAFE iteration equation

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